

**Learning
Technology
Accelerator**

D3.4 Framework for basic technical infrastructure

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report is Deliverable D3.4 connected to task 3.4 in the 3rd work package and is part of MS3 of the LEA project. The leader of the work package is Otto-von-Guericke-University, who also compiled the deliverable. Task 3.4 includes a state-of-the-art report for key elements of school infrastructures.

1.1 Purpose of the report

In previous reports, the needs of students, teachers and parents have been identified (D3.2) and a recommendation of key elements for a Personal Learning Environment (PLE) has been developed (D3.3). This report describes the necessary infrastructure to fulfill these needs and using PLEs. Additionally, the key elements and minimum requirements for a basic infrastructure in schools will be identified.

1.2 Approach and Methodology

IT equipment in schools plays a decisive role in the successful use of digital teaching and learning tools, both for teachers and students.

In order to make recommendations for the IT infrastructure required for the use of digital teaching and learning tools, the results of relevant studies were evaluated as part of a literature search (Survey of Schools: ICT in Education and ICILS 2013). This evaluation will be complemented by an evaluation of the results of the online survey on the required competence of teachers and students for the use of digital teaching and learning tools and possible barriers that prevent their use on both sides. This survey was conducted with participants from Germany, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, Spain and Hungary (D3.2).

The evaluation of the different studies is complemented by the results of the teaching group of the Institute for Simulation and Graphics of the Faculty of

Computer Science of the Otto-von-Guericke-University Magdeburg. Within this working group scientists are working on digitization concepts for general schools in the Magdeburg area. In cooperation with the state of Saxony-Anhalt, 2XXX has developed the classroom of the future and the demonstration center of the state of Saxony-Anhalt for school IT and digital learning tools. In both projects, concepts for school IT were developed and practically implemented and tested with partner schools. The expertise of the scientists in the working group and the findings from the implementation of the IT concepts at schools in Magdeburg were primarily incorporated into the design of the questionnaire for D 3.2 and were taken into account in the evaluation of the results.

2. REQUIREMENTS AND BARRIERS FOR A SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGY IN SCHOOLS

To determine the current level of technical infrastructure in European schools, we included specific questions regarding the technical infrastructure into a survey we distributed between the partner countries of the LEA project. 297 teachers and 981 students participated. In the following, the results are presented and discussed. Technical infrastructure in LEA partner schools – Teachers Questions

2.1 Technical infrastructure in LEA partner schools – Teachers Questions

ID19: Please indicate the technical equipment your school is equipped with.

This question was intended to check the current state of IT at the partner schools. The teachers could choose from the following answer options. Multiple choices were possible.

Table 1: Distribution of answers to ID19 per country in percent

Option	DE	FI	IT	PT	ES	HU	Ø
computer cabinet	58,9	21,4	43,8	47,9	54,3	87,5	50,8
mobile laptop cart	24,7	78,6	2,2	8,3	48,6	8,3	21,9
laptops	41,1	67,9	12,4	6,3	57,1	79,2	34,3
internet access in certain rooms	64,4	78,6	25,8	54,2	28,6	95,8	50,8
interactive displays in some rooms	56,2	46,4	32,6	45,8	42,9	83,3	47,1
interactive displays in all rooms	26,0	78,6	21,3	2,1	40,0	29,2	27,6
printer	61,6	85,7	20,2	41,7	57,1	75,0	48,8
camera	23,3	64,3	12,4	14,6	34,3	37,5	24,9
WIFI everywhere	30,1	96,4	11,2	20,8	51,4	50,0	33,3

For a better comparison, the data is presented as a mosaic plot as well as a bar chart sorted on the basis of the total data set in the following figures.

Figure 1: Ranking of items of ID19 over all countries

Figure 2: Distribution of answers to ID19 per country in percent (plot)

Results discussion

As shown by the bar chart “computer cabinets” and “internet access in certain rooms” (both 50,8%) are what most schools are equipped with,

while "camera" (24,9%) and "laptop cart" (21,9%) were indicated the least. However there are some significant differences between the participating countries.

For instance only 21,4% of Finnish teachers stated that they have computer cabinets in their schools. The results suggest, that the cabinets are replaced by mobile laptop carts (78,6% in FI) or laptops (67,9% in FI). An argument might be that, the more laptops there are, the less computer cabinets are needed and therefore indicated. Considering the relationship between the variables "computer cabinet" and "laptop" or "laptop cart", however, a ϕ -coefficient of approx. 0,24 shows that there is only a weak to medium relationship between these variables. In detail, the majority of teachers (37,4%) have selected both the item "computer cabinet" and at least one of the items "laptop" or "laptop cart". 62,0% of schools are equipped with laptops or laptop cart, 50,8% with a computer cabinet. Accordingly, it can be assumed that both technologies are (still) relevant in everyday school. Also, there is no strong connection between the items "computer cabinet" and "internet access in certain rooms" ($\phi \approx 0,18$). Consequently, it cannot be assumed that schools equipped with desktop PCs are more likely to have a (possibly wired) internet connection only in selected rooms, while schools equipped with laptops or mobile devices are more likely to use wireless Internet. Both solutions are prevalent.

Strong country-specific differences are furthermore visible in a variety of other items. Of all participating countries, Hungary has the highest percentage of "internet access in certain rooms" (97,5%), while Italy has the lowest (25,8%). The same is true for interactive displays in all rooms, where the difference between Finland (87,6%) and Portugal (2,1%) is considerable. These differences make it necessary to have a model for a school IT infrastructure that is modular and flexible and therefore able to adapt to the different situations at schools. A suitable infrastructure must both provide a sufficiently strong network as well as possibilities to manage

various end devices such as interactive boards and displays, laptops, smartphones etc. in the network. The administration of such a school IT network cannot then be a task of the teachers (especially with regard to the various prerequisites), but must be carried out by appropriately qualified personnel. The need for support is also reflected in another question asked to teachers during the survey and already considered in D3.2. There teachers were supposed to indicate aspects that would support them when using digital learning tools (see D3.2 - question ID09). It became clear that the majority of respondents were in favour of IT support (67,7%). Of these, 19,2% indicated external IT support and a majority of 48,5% in-school IT support.

ID20: Please indicate which classroom equipment you need for the use of learning software.

With this question the teachers were asked to indicate, what kind of equipment is important for them, when using digital learning tools. The teachers could choose from the following answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table 2: Distribution of answers to ID20 per country in percent

Option	DE	FI	IT	PT	ES	HU	Ø
computer	54,8	53,6	62,9	45,8	37,1	54,2	53,5
laptop	53,4	75,0	13,5	20,8	37,1	70,8	37,7
mobile devices	17,8	71,4	30,3	27,1	65,7	54,2	36,7
internet access	63,0	82,1	58,4	54,2	68,6	83,3	64,3
classroom management	71,2	21,4	21,3	25,0	37,1	58,3	39,1
interactive displays	46,6	82,1	57,3	22,9	48,6	70,8	51,5
printer	47,9	64,3	30,3	14,6	11,4	54,2	35,0
cloud / school network	42,5	53,6	21,3	20,8	48,6	45,8	34,7
replacement devices	41,1	39,3	21,3	12,5	37,1	16,7	27,9

For a better comparison, the data is presented as a mosaic plot as well as a bar chart sorted on the basis of the total data set in the following figures.

Figure 3: Ranking of items of ID20 over all countries

Figure 4: Distribution of answers to ID20 per country in percent (plot)

Results discussion

As shown by the bar chart there are three items that were indicated more frequently: "internet access" (64,3%), "computer" (53,5%) and "interactive displays" (both 51,5%), while a "school network" (34,7%) and "replacement devices" (27,9%) are valued as least important for using learning software. A mixed picture emerges regarding the use of "computers", "laptops" or "mobile devices".

It can be seen that teachers from Finland and Hungary consider laptops more important (FI: 75,4%, HU: 70,8%), while those from Portugal or Italy consider computers more important (PT: 45,8%, IT: 62,9%). The assessment of interactive displays is similar. Here, too, teachers from Finland rate their importance as rather high (FI: 82,1%; HU: 70,8%), while the rest consider them less important. One possible reason could be that the importance of devices is considered higher in especially those countries that have a higher degree of equipment with them. Considering the contingency between the equipment of "interactive displays in some/all rooms" from ID19 and the assessment of "interactive displays" as significant from ID20 as an example, a medium connection ($\phi \approx 0,36$) results. There is therefore a correlation between the availability of the devices (such as an interactive display) and the perceived benefit. Consequently, the purchase of new IT equipment is only effective if the users (teachers) are able to use it in a meaningful way. Question ID09 (see D3.2 or results discussion of the previous question) also shows that this cannot be assumed a priori. Here, the demand for support by media pedagogically trained personnel as well as by a material database was also surveyed. The results also indicate the need for pedagogical support (media pedagogically trained personnel: 28,0%; exchange with other teachers: 51,5%; cloud with materials: 44,8%). For a more generic comparison the following figure shows the answers to ID19 (existing equipment) with those from ID20 (demanded equipment) in 5 categories.

Figure 5: Comparison of answers of ID19 and ID20

For the category "mobile devices" the items "mobile laptop cart" and "laptop" for ID19 as well as the items "laptop" and "mobile devices" for ID20 were combined for reference. It becomes clear that the biggest difference between actual status and demand lies in the equipment with a suitable network as well as with interactive whiteboards, while the equipment and terminals roughly correspond to the demand.

ID21: Please indicate which type of equipment you prefer.

The last question for teachers about the technical equipment was related to different kind of settings for schools. In general, there are two distinct possibilities: either every student has the exact same equipment to work with or each student can bring his/her own device.

Table 3: Distribution of answers to ID21 per country in percent

Option	DE	FI	IT	PT	ES	HU	□
same equipment	84,1	92,6	86,1	83,3	72,4	87,5	84,5
BYOD	15,9	7,4	13,9	16,7	27,6	12,5	15,5

Figure 6: Distribution of answers to ID21 per country in percent (plot)

Results discussion

From the results, the trend towards uniform devices for all teachers and students is evident (84,5%). In the country comparison, all results are above the 80% mark, only the Spanish teachers with 72,4% tend a bit more towards the BYOD-approach. Looking at the relationship between the response trend for ID21 and the response "laptop" or "mobile device" for ID20, the relationship is only weak ($\varphi \approx 0,13$). Therefore it cannot be assumed that teachers who preferably use mobile devices also tend to support the BYOD approach.

2.2 Technical infrastructure in LEA partner schools – Students Questions

This question was intended to check the current state of IT at the partner schools from the view of the students. For this question, the students could choose between the following options. Multiple answers could be given.

Table 4: Distribution of answers to IDS15 per country in percent

Option	DE	FI	IT	PT	ES	HU	Ø
computer cabinet	79,6	23,3	73,9	93,3	89,4	98,4	76,8
mobile laptop cart	27,9	80,6	14,8	2,2	46,8	19,5	30,9
laptops	56,7	59,2	43,2	22,2	40,4	82,8	56,8
internet access in certain rooms	69,6	67,0	46,6	80	59,6	75,0	68,0
interactive displays in some rooms	60,5	41,7	40,9	71,1	48,9	83,6	59,7
interactive displays in all rooms	36,5	58,3	39,8	17,8	51,1	33,6	38,5
printer	76,3	79,6	39,8	68,9	76,6	81,3	73,7
camera	38,6	47,6	31,8	2,2	12,8	68,0	39,9
WIFI everywhere	44,6	85,4	25,0	40,0	57,4	42,2	47,2

For a better comparison, the data is presented as a mosaic plot as well as a bar chart sorted on the basis of the total data set in the following figures.

Figure 7: Ranking of items of IDS15 over all countries

Figure 8: Distribution of answers to IDS15 per country in percent (plot)

Results discussion

As shown by the bar chart “computer cabinets” (76,8%) and “internet access in certain rooms” (73,7%) are what most schools are equipped with, while “interactive displays in all rooms” (38,5%) and “mobile laptop cart” (30,9%) were indicated the least. However there are some significant differences between the participating countries.

For instance only 23,3% (-53,5% to average) of Finnish students stated that they have computer cabinets in their schools. The results suggest, that the cabinets are replaced by mobile laptop carts (80,6% in FI; +49,7% to average) or laptops (59,2% in FI; +2,4% to average). However similarly to ID19 a fairly low relation ($\phi \approx 0,24$) between the variables "computer cabinet" and "laptop" or "laptop cart" underlines the finding from ID19 that it can be assumed that both technologies are (still) relevant in everyday school. This in turn also underlines the need for a model for a school IT

infrastructure that is modular and flexible and therefore able to adapt to the different situations at schools.

IDS16: Specify which devices/ equipment you need to work with learning software. With this question the students were asked to indicate, what kind of equipment is important for them, when using digital learning tools. For this question, students could choose from the following possible answers. Multiple choices were possible.

Table 5: Ranking of items of IDS16 over all countries

Option	DE	FI	IT	PT	ES	HU	Ø
computer	74,2	49,5	62,5	93,3	83,0	92,2	74,2
laptop	57,9	52,4	36,4	37,8	63,8	83,6	58,1
mobile devices	66,5	83,5	39,8	57,8	63,8	72,7	66,2
internet access	80,9	79,6	61,4	88,9	70,2	91,4	80,2
interactive displays	38,4	24,3	46,6	55,6	42,6	43,0	39,2
printer	21,1	20,4	19,3	33,3	44,7	12,5	21,4

For a better comparison, the data is presented as a mosaic plot as well as a bar chart sorted on the basis of the total data set in the following figures.

Figure 9: Ranking of items of IDS16 over all countries

Figure 10: Distribution of answers to IDS16 per country in percent (plot)

Results discussion

As shown by the bar chart “internet access” (80,2%) is the most indicated item, while “interactive displays” (39,2%) and “printers” (21,4%) are valued as least important for using learning software. A mixed picture emerges regarding the use of “computers”, “laptops” or “mobile devices”.

It can be seen that students from Finland consider mobile devices more important (FI: 83,5%; +17,3% to average), while those from Portugal and Hungary consider computers far more important (PT: 93,3%, HU: 92,2%). The assessment of internet access yields similar results for each country, with Italy (61,4%; -18,8% to average) being an exception. Interactive displays are rated similarly across each country as well, with the exception of Finland (24,3%; -14,9% to average).

IDS17: What type of devices do you prefer when using learning software in class?
 With this question, students were supposed to choose between two different options of learning peripherals, either bringing their own devices (BYOD) or being equipped with devices from the school.

Table 6: Distribution of answers to ID21 per country in percent

Option	DE	FI	IT	PT	ES	HU	Ø
own devices	67,5	71,7	78,8	46,5	61,4	66,1	67,6
devices that belong to school	32,5	28,3	21,2	53,5	38,6	33,9	32,4

Figure 11: Distribution of answers to IDS17 per country in percent (plot)

Results discussion

In contrast to the related teacher question, there is a trend towards using their own devices by the students (67,6%). Only 32,4% prefer devices, that belong to the school. Since this question is not exactly the same as the related question ID21 for teachers, “own device” does not necessarily mean that these devices need to be individual and different. Also school devices can be diverse as well. But if we combine the answers of the students and teacher questions, we get the result, that uniform devices,

owned by the students, could be a good choice to accommodate both, students and teachers. This in turn makes it necessary to develop a basic requirement description for end devices to be used in schools depending on the subject and the individual school.

2.3 Technical infrastructure in european schools

In a survey conducted by the European Commission, various aspects of ICT in Education were examined in an international, European comparison. Among others, the Survey of Schools: ICT in Education shows that the digital school has the following IT equipment:

a corresponding number of digital devices in working order

desktop and laptop computers

e-readers

mobile phones

interactive whiteboards

digital cameras

data projectors in classrooms

internet connection

broadband access (ADSL, cable, etc.)

broadband speed (above or below 10 mbps)

concept for support and maintenance

internal or external

other components

local area network

email addresses for teachers and students

website for the school and activities in school

virtual learning environment

These four points are the indicators for IT equipment in digital schools. In the context of these points, functionality and regular use in class and in everyday school life play a decisive role. The study does not further investigate the interconnectedness and self-image of teachers and

students in using digital teaching and learning systems, but these are also important characteristics of school IT-Infrastructure.

The above components of an IT equipment can be extended by further components. The concept of the hardware components can easily be extended by standard software (word processing, spreadsheet and presentation creation). In addition to the various components of an IT infrastructure in schools, support and the pupil-computer ratio also play an important role. The International Computer and Information Literacy Study examines, among other things, the pupil-computer ratio in an international comparison of countries. On average, 11.6 students in Europe have access to a computer in their school. In a comparison of OECD countries, the figure is 15.3 and in an international comparison 18.0 students per computer. Support for IT equipment includes not only the maintenance of existing hardware and software, but also the procurement of new equipment and the selection of the software to be used. For the comprehensive tasks of supporting the IT equipment of a school, there is talk of an IT coordinator. This coordinator takes care of all these issues within the framework of the technical and pedagogical support of the IT equipment. A regular exchange with the teachers and the school management is a decisive necessity.

3. REQUIREMENTS FOR TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN SCHOOLS

Based on the results from the questionnaires (see chapter 2.1 and 2.2) and the desktop research (see chapter 2.3), there is a list of needed equipment items for teachers and students. These items require a certain technical infrastructure so that they can be used in the classroom. These are the technical requirements for school infrastructure.

Besides doing the quantitative analysis via the questionnaires, there were needs analysis workshops performed in the LEA project, from which a list of key elements for personal learning environments has been developed (see LEA Deliverable 3.3). These key elements are derived from real classroom needs and describe the kind of learning tools and scenarios teachers and students think are most important for them. These elements lead to further requirements for the technical school infrastructure.

3.1 Requirements from a technical perspective

The evaluation of the questionnaires and our desktop research shows that there exists a variety of technical scenarios in the schools, with each scenario still being relevant and used by teachers. While teachers prefer uniform devices for the whole class, students would rather use their own devices. The infrastructure therefore needs to support both, and not just mobile devices but computer labs as well.

The usage of mobile devices requires the availability of WIFI in the whole school building with advanced role concepts and in a high quality (bandwidth and speed). Data security and privacy aspects need to be taken care of in a flexible way, so that teachers and students and any other kind of users can be serviced accordingly.

When using a number of devices in the classroom, special management systems are needed to support teachers with mechanisms for sharing and collaboration. This can be done in computer labs or when using school owned devices which all have the same configuration. The infrastructure

should provide options to connect devices in different networks, for instance, a special network for one classroom, where all devices including the teachers computer and interactive display can communicate with each other without interference.

3.2 Requirements from a learning perspective

The results of the workshop evaluation (D3.3) show that personal learning environments (PLE) play an important role in the education landscape of the 21st century. The use of PLE's in schools can be done via cloud services or a school owned server, or a combination of both. Additionally, there are key elements of a PLE that needs to be supported.

PLE supports creativity

To support creativity and collaboration, the appropriate tools generally need network connections, both internal and to the internet. When using design thinking tools with a larger number of people, interactive displays with a high resolution are needed as well as computers or laptops for each participant.

PLEs should save teacher's time when preparing and evaluating lessons, that means that technology should work "out of the box" without time consuming configuration.

PLE has an innovative UID

Innovative user interfaces do not only use standard input and output, but new technologies like touch screens, interactive pens, gestures or QR-codes. It is important that a variety of technologies can be supported and that interactive displays and convertible devices are equipped with the appropriate components.

PLE is independent and connected

Each student needs her own device when using a PLE, and this can be a school owned device or a device the students already has and brings to

school. The infrastructure therefore has to support the BYOD approach (bring your own device).

PLE boosts speed

The requirement from the PLE is a intuitive and easy design to make the time of active usage as short as possible for a given task. That means, that all supporting processes like logging in or sending data needs to be fast as well. In schools, there can be a large number of users on the system at the same time, and the infrastructure architecture needs to be scalable and fast for this use case.

PLE supports different models of blended learning

When students personalize their learning, they design not only their own learning paths, but also their learning in their own time and space. All content should be available not only at school but also from home or other places outside of the school at all times. That needs a system with high availability and a large amount of storage space for the various kinds of contents. This can be done on a cloud service or with a school server, or both.

PLE uses learning analytics

Learning analytics include highly sensitive student data that must be secured and can only be accessible by authorized persons.

PLE for lifelong learning

To support lifelong learning, open and widely used standards and protocols for data transfer should be supported, that allow to export and import data between different systems.

PLE uses game mechanics

Gamification in education means to include game mechanics into teaching and learning. This usually means higher requirements for speed and performance, and possibly devices for virtual reality. An extensible

school infrastructure allows for adding components without taking off power from existing configurations.

PLE uses automated online assistance

Modern PLEs use artificial intelligence mechanisms to guide students through the learning process not only during the school day, but everytime the student is actively using it. To give feedback to the students and also to teachers and parents, there are interfaces needed to E-Mail-Systems or other notification services.

PLE uses cloud computing

To use cloud services, the school needs a reliable and high-performance internet connection. When using external services, the regulation of the GDPR has to be respected and the provider carefully selected. But then a professional service for schools is available with less administrative effort.

3.3 Layer architecture for school infrastructure

Due to the diversity of the above listed requirements, the basic infrastructure for schools needs to be scalable and flexible. A layer architecture is the technology to implement scalability (see Figure 12 on the next page).

Level 2 – Digital learning tools

Interactive presentation technology in the classroom

Computer room (optional), VDI

smartphone usage

BYOD

Level 1 – Infrastructure II

Schools own servers (optional)

e.g. necessary for:

- local data storage if the schools internet bandwidth is low
- usage of desktop virtualizations

Managed Wi-Fi throughout the building, ≥ 1 accesspoint in every room

Level 0 – Infrastructure I

Level 0 describes the lower technological level, the interface where the school is connected to the outside world. Level 0 consists of the internet connection (e.g. via DSL, optic fibre, ...), a firewall and managed Gigabit connections via cable and WIFI throughout the building with at least one access point in every room. The firewall is important to ensure the security of the ICT systems. Managed network connections allow for a sophisticated role concept and can be configured to meet the actual needs of a certain school. Nevertheless, the configuration makes it possible to adapt and change whenever school policy requests new regulations. By providing access points to each room and managed WIFI connection throughout the whole building, there is enough bandwidth to connect a whole class of students via stationary and mobile devices to the internet at the same time. All this requires a high every day availability of service and should ideally be outsourced and not be administered by the school. It is important that all these services are available to each teacher and student without any need for configuration or special knowledge, just like any other infrastructure in the school, e.g. water or electrical power.

Level 1 describes another level of infrastructure. It is optional and depends on the exact configuration of level 0 and the needs of the school. This allows for flexibility. On level 1, you find school owned servers, if the school decides to have local storage space. They might need it because there is no cloud service or due to security reasons. Also, if the bandwidth of the internet connection is low, local servers make working and collaboration between students faster. If on level 2 a solution with desktop virtualization is used, on level 1 this will be administered.

Level 2 is the level of digital learning tools, the level on which teachers and students are working. Here we find the digital equipment for everyday work. The lower levels provide the foundation that is needed so that on level 2 all the diverse environments and configurations teachers need can be used. There can be computer cabinets with either stationary PCs or terminals with

desktop virtualization, and there also can be students using smartphones or other own devices via the school WIFI. It supports interactive displays in some or every classroom and provides access to personal learning environments and other learning software. This is also the level a school administrator should be working on, configuring the classroom environments or management software and supporting teachers during their everyday use of digital media in the classroom.

3.4 Recommendations for selected infrastructure items

The exact technical requirements for all components of the school infrastructure depend on the size of the school and the number of people working and learning there. But even in elementary schools with only 4 grades and small classes, there are about 200 persons (students and teachers) who might be using the infrastructure all at the same time. Therefore, schools need a professional solution to provide a reliable and secure school infrastructure. This is not a task a school can and should solve. It is recommended that all level 0 infrastructure is provided by experts from outside the schools. Recommended minimum requirements:

- Internet access: 100mBit connection
- Access points: one per 20 devices, at least one per classroom, additional access points in floors and offices
- school server: high-availability server, redundant systems
- interactive display: 65" screen size, integrated loudspeakers, multi-touch

4. CONCLUSION

To support teachers and students and provide them with the infrastructure that is needed to use digital learning tools in the classroom, a modular solution is recommended. There are services that are not the core responsibility of a school. The basic ICT infrastructure should be provided by professionals, just as other infrastructures like water or electrical power.

On higher levels, schools need dedicated personal for the administration of classroom configuration or to support teachers in their everyday work.

The layer architecture described in chapter 3.4 is a model architecture and can be implemented by using various software and devices. To better support teachers and help school administrators, there is a need for special designed software systems, especially on the interface between level 1 and 2.

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